

A Review Paper on use of Plastic Bottel Fibres and Foundry Sand as Partial Replacement of Aggregate in Concrete

Mithilesh Kumar Singh¹, Nitesh Kushwah²

¹M. Tech. Scholar, ²Professor

^{1,2}Department of Civil Engineering, Millennium Institute of Technology, Bhopal, Madhya Pradesh, India

How to cite this paper: Mithilesh Kumar Singh | Nitesh Kushwah "A Review Paper on use of Plastic Bottel Fibres and Foundry Sand as Partial Replacement of Aggregate in Concrete" Published in International Journal of Trend in Scientific Research and Development (ijtsrd), ISSN: 2456-6470, Volume-3 | Issue-5, August 2019, pp.2635-2638, <https://doi.org/10.31142/ijtsrd29312>

IJTSRD29312

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Literature Survey

General

In this section an elaborative talk is made with respect to works done as such far around there as writing audit. Natural course aggregate & fine aggregate is getting depleted due to large-scale construction. So it is important to find out an alternative of natural aggregate, which can be used as partial replacement of natural course aggregate & fine aggregate. There are many types of waste material/byproducts that are explored for attainable use in concrete as a partial replacement of course aggregate & fine aggregate mixture. Such sorts of materials are coal bottom ash recycled fine mixture, sewerage sludge ash, stone dust and glass cullet, and waste foundry sand, waste plastic scrap, fiber waste etc.

1. **Younus Maqbool 2019** Concrete with 1%, 2%, 2.5%, 3% and 5% PET bottle fibers for fine aggregate were produced and compared against control mix with no replacement. Cube specimens, cylinder specimens and prism specimens were cast, cured and tested for 7 day and 28 days strength. Tests such as Compression test, splitting tensile test and flexural strength tests were done and the results were compared with control specimens and results were compared. The observed results revealed an increase in compression and tensile strength hence with the increasing demand for fine aggregate, PET bottle fiber replacements can be adopted. This study was carried to investigate the

INTRODUCTION

The most generally acknowledged solution for this flexural shortcoming of cement is the regular fortification with high quality steel. Regardless of the way that these procedures offer flexibility to people, they however don't grow the trademark unbending nature of solid itself. In like manner the help putting and profitable compaction of RCC is amazingly troublesome if the solid is of low workability especially by virtue of overpowering solid (M-25). In plain concrete and near feeble materials, assistant parts (scaled down scale breaks) become even before stacking, particularly on account of drying shrinkage or distinctive purposes behind volume change. The width of these breaks on occasion outperforms a few microns, yet their two estimations may be of higher enormity.

➤ **Foundry waste sand:** Foundry sand is clean, uniformly sized, high-quality silica sand and it is used to form molds for ferrous (iron and steel) and nonferrous (copper, aluminum, brass) metal castings. Specific Gravity of foundry sand is 2.55 and bulk density is 1650 kg/m³.

Foundry sand is clean, uniformly sized, high quality silica sand, used in foundry casting processes. The sand is bonded to form molds or patterns used for ferrous (iron and steel) and non-ferrous (copper, aluminum, brass) metal castings. Shake-out sand from completed metal casting are often reclaimed back into the foundry sand process.

- properties of concrete with plastic pet (bottle) fibres as partial replacement of fine aggregates.
2. **Rudiele Schankoski 2019** The use of waste materials in the building industry is a major challenge for eco-efficient construction. Brazil generates more than 3 million tons of waste foundry sand (WFS) annually, making it one of the largest industrial wastes produced in the country. This work proposes the use of WFS in two novel ways: in conventional concrete by WFS calcination, and in dry-mix concrete for the production of concrete blocks. For the conventional mixture study, mortars with 0, 50 and 100% replacement of natural sand by WFS and calcined WFS (CFS) were produced. The fresh state properties, volumetric variation, cement hydration and 28-days.
3. **L.R. Prudêncio Jr 2019** This work investigated the use of diabase (D) and gneiss (G) quarry powders as alternatives to limestone filler (L) for self-compacting concrete (SCC) production. For this, SCCs with the different quarry powders, each one in three different particle size distributions, were produced. The shape and texture of the particles were evaluated through SEM image analysis. The fresh state properties of the SCCs were evaluated by the workability tests slump flow, V-Funnel, J-ring and VSI, and by rheometry.

4. **Divya.M.R (et al.), (2018)**, were concluded that Among the various mixes it was observed at the age of 28 days the maximum strength attained at 15% of foundry sand with 10% of cow dung ash. Use of cow dung ash in higher proportion reduces the strength and hence, a constant value of 10% is maintained throughout the project. This concrete preparation is eco-friendly and cost effective. The degree of workability of concrete was normal with the addition of Cow Dung Ash and Foundry sand for M20 grade concrete. The main advantage being reduction of environmentally hazardous material and increasing the strength of concrete to a considerable percentage.
5. **Raissa Ferron 2017** The influence of the mineralogy and particle size distribution was evaluated by rheological methods on cement pastes containing the materials under investigation. In addition, in-situ particle size analysis of the fresh pastes was conducted to observe how these different by-product dusts affect agglomeration kinetics. Pastes containing quarry powders showed lower yield stress and lower viscosity than pastes containing only cement.
6. **Arivalagan.S' 2017** Tests were conducted to determine the properties of plastic aggregate such as density and specific gravity. As 100% replacement of natural fine aggregate with plastic fine aggregate is not feasible, partial replacement at various percentage were examined. The percentage substitution that gave higher compressive strength was used for determining the other properties such as modulus of elasticity, split tensile strength and flexural strength. Higher compressive strength was found with 10% natural fine aggregate replaced concrete.
7. **Dsouza, V., (2017)** were concluded that the From the results of characterization of material, Workability of Concrete, Compressive Strength Test, Split Tensile Strength Test and Flexural Strength Test on M25 grade of concrete, made of different mixes with 10%, 20%, 30%, 40% and 50% replacement level of Waste Foundry Sand. By comparing the compressive strength of specimen with different replacement level following conclusions can be made i. For the grade of concrete considered for the study at 0.45 water cement ratio, Mix-2 i.e. the ratio of 80:20 of Conventional Sand: Foundry Sand has proved to be having optimum ratio which gives maximum Compressive strength of all ratios. ii. At the higher replacement levels of 30%, 40% and 50% the strength decreases considerably when compared to that of NC mix.
8. **Omanakuttan Athira, 2017** Half breed Fibre-fortified cement is a composite material comprising of blends of bond, fine total, coarse total, steel fibre and glass fibre. The half breed fiber fortified solid displays better weakness quality and expanded static and dynamic rigidity. In this task, the quality of fibre strengthened cement was explored with incomplete supplanting of bond with rice husk slag and fly fiery debris. Steel fibre and glass fibre was included the request of 0.25%, 0.5% and 0.75% by volume of concrete and 0.25%, 0.5% and 0.75% by weight of bond. Rice Husk Ash was utilized to supplant conventional Portland bond by 20% and fly powder 20% by weight of concrete extent.
9. **Manhal A Jibrael 2016** his paper presents a method of strengthen concrete by the addition of percentages recycled waste plastic (polyethylene). Almost 126 samples of concrete are prepared, the concrete Strength (compressive, splitting tensile and flexural strength) are investigated along a time interval of 7 to 28 days using 1%, 3% and 5% from fine aggregate recycled waste plastic (polyethylene). It is found that when waste plastic bottles increased from zero to 5% of the sand in the mix.
10. **Salahaldein Alsadey 2016** The plastic fibers were added from 0.0% to 3.0%. The compressive strengths of concrete were determined after 28 days of curing period and compared with control concrete. Experiments done shows increase in compressive strength by 12%. Plastic bottle fibre additive can be adopted. The plastic bottle fibre reduces the quantity of industry fibers used in concrete and also plastic bottle fibre is proved to be more economical.
11. **Aswani Sabu and Thomas Paul, 2016** Fibers are generally used as a common engineering material for crack resistance and strengthening of concrete. Their properties and characteristics greatly influence the properties of concrete which has been proved already in many previous researches. Accordingly it has been found that steel fibers give the maximum strength in comparison to glass and polypropylene fibers. In this experimental study, two types of steel fibers namely hooked end and crimped fibers are used. The volume fractions taken are 0.75%, 1.0% and 1.25% and M30 grade concrete is adopted. Cement has been replaced with 25% of Class F flash. The primary focus is to compare the mechanical properties of concrete using both fibres.
12. **R. Madheswaran, S. Arun Singh, K.S. Sathyanarayanan 2014** Concrete is likely the most broadly utilized development material on the planet. The primary fixing in the regular cement is Portland concrete. The measure of bond generation produces around rise to measure of carbon dioxide into the climate. Concrete creation is devouring noteworthy measure of characteristic assets. That has brought weights to lessen bond utilization by the utilization of supplementary materials. Accessibility of mineral admixtures checked opening of another period for planning solid blend of ever more elevated quality. Fly Ash and silica smolder is another mineral admixture, whose potential isn't completely used. Also just restricted investigations have been completed in India on the utilization of silica smolder for the improvement of high quality cement with expansion of steel strands. The examination centers around the compressive quality execution of the mixed cement containing diverse level of silica smoke and Fly Ash and steel fiber as an incomplete substitution of OPC. The bond in concrete is supplanted as needs be with Silica seethe content was use from 0% to 10% in the interim of 2% in weight premise and furthermore fly cinder content was use from 10% in weight premise. So to enhance the quality of solid steel filaments were included 0.5%, 1%, 1.5%, 2% by weight of steel fiber. Solid 3D shapes are tried at the age of 3, 7, and 28 days of curing. At last, the

quality execution of Fly slag and silica fume mixed fiber fortified cement is contrasted and the execution of customary cement. From the exploratory examinations, it has been watched that, the ideal substitution Fly fume remains and silica fume to bond and steel fiber without changing much the compressive quality is 10% - 8 % and 1.5 % individually for M25 review Concrete

13. Hoe Kwan Mahyuddin Ramli, 2015 Notwithstanding being presented to chloride and sulfate assaults, marine structures are liable to seismic and affect loads coming about because of waves, affect with strong protests, and water transports. Accordingly, the flexural conduct and effect protection of Fiber-Reinforced Concrete (FRC) in marine condition must be clarified. Nonetheless, such data is barely announced. Along these lines, this examination plans to investigate the impacts of mimicked forceful conditions on flexural quality and effect protection of FRC and to recognize the connection between the two parameters. Three sorts of filaments, specifically, coconut fiber, Barsrap fiber (BF), and soluble base safe glass fiber, were utilized as a part of this investigation. The fiber measurements extended from 0.6% to 2.4% of the cover volume. All blends have consistent water/cement proportion of 0.37 and their compressive qualities were all surpassing 60 MPa. The examples were arranged and presented to three diverse forceful presentation situations, in particular, tropical atmosphere, cyclic air and seawater conditions, and seawater condition for up to 180 days. Results demonstrate that flexural quality and effect protection of FRC have an immediate association with fiber content. Regardless, change in fiber content is more critical than expanding fiber dose in improving flexural quality yet modification in the two issues would fundamentally affect the effect protection. Rigidity of an individual BF (640 MPa) is significantly higher than the flexural quality of the BFRC composite. Along these lines, disappointment of solid lattice was seen to happen preceding the crack of the fiber which thusly brought about fiber haul out from the solid grid. Among the different FRC analyzed, FRC containing the most elevated BF content (2.4%) exhibited the best flexural quality execution. The flexural quality of the Bar strap FRC was seen to be expanded by 11- 13% in all presentation situations following 180 days. The pre-break vitality ingestions, which were resolved through effect stack test, were found to increment by 60- 63% when contrasted with the control solid, which showed no post-split vitality assimilation. In the interim, the post-break vitality retentions of the 2.4BF were found to go between 3.67 J and 3.71 J for different ecological introduction conditions. Examination of fluctuation (ANOVA) comes about demonstrated that flexural qualities were fundamentally expanded following a half year of presentation to the different forceful condition conditions, particularly in seawater. This could be because of arrangement of salt gems which contributed towards improving the fiber/lattice frictional bond. Notwithstanding, the presentation situations have no noteworthy impact on affect protection execution.

14. Su-Jin Lee, 2014 In this investigation, basic nano-engineered and steel filaments were utilized to lessen the measure of steel rebar appropriated in precast

fortified solid composite individuals. The flexural execution of the individuals was assessed utilizing longitudinal steel proportions of 1.65 and 1.20 and a transverse steel proportion of 0.20. Cross breed fiber blends comprising of different measures of auxiliary nano-manufactured and snared end steel filaments were utilized as fortifying materials alongside the steel rebar. The nano-manufactured fiber volume parts were 0.4, 0.5, and 0.6 vol. %, and the steel fiber substance were 5, 10, and 20 kg/m³. Flexural execution tests were completed for the subsequent half breed fiber-strengthened bond composites. The test outcomes exhibited that the half breed fiber-fortified concrete composites fulfilled the essential conditions to supplant the general strengthening bars as per the RILEM standard when the blend contained 0.4 vol. % of nano-manufactured fiber and 20 kg/m³ of steel fiber. The flexural conduct of a 350 * 180 * 1500-mm precast composite part fortified by such a half and half fiber blend and steel rebar was assessed; its most extreme load was 30% more noteworthy than the outlined extreme load and 3.5% more prominent than that of a steel fiber-strengthened composite part. The material execution of cement with a half and half blend of fortifying basic nano-engineered and steel filaments was assessed. The best blend was then tried in a precast RC composite part utilizing the most reduced conceivable steel proportion to assess the flexural execution.

Problem identification

- The construction industry is the area where the safe use of foundry waste sand with plastic bottles scrap is possible.
- When it is introduced in concrete as a replacement material, it reduces space problem and also reduces the cost of concrete.
- There is no investigation performed on foundry waste sand with plastic bottles scrap to use in construction industries.

Objectives

The objectives of the research are outlined below:

- To study the concrete properties by using waste foundry sand as partial replacement of natural sand & plastic bottle scrap as partial replacement of course aggregate.

Conclusion

Waste plastic bottle scrap & foundry sand for its compressive, tensile and flexural strength in concrete mix made as partial replacement of natural aggregate increase strength as compare to conventional concrete.

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